
Location plan

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Deliverable D 6.4: Report on sustainable large-scale photobioreactor locations in the EU including their demands to allow for certification

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I. List of abbreviations:

ENGL	European Network of GMOs Laboratories
EU	European Union
GMM	Genetically Modified Microorganism
GMO	Genetically Modified Organisms
HAZAN	Hazard Analysis
HAZOP	Hazard and Operability Study
MPL	Multiplate photobioreactor
NRL	National Reference Laboratories
PBR	Photobioreactor
WP	Work package

II. About PhotoSynH2 project:

Since the launch of the Green Deal, the EU set out the paramount goal to reach climate neutrality by 2050 by stimulating decarbonization of all sectors of the economy, and specifically reducing green gas emission. To achieve that transitioning towards a safe, affordable, resilient and decarbonised EU energy system is considered a strategic objective.

Hydrogen can contribute to these end as it allows to use renewable energy, can enhance the decarbonization of heavy industrial sectors and has the potential to link together different source of energy vectors such as power or gas.

To date, hydrogen is mainly produced from fossil fuels. However, efforts are being made to produce hydrogen using technologies with zero life-cycle greenhouse gas emissions, or direct conversion of renewable heat or biomass and biowaste processing.

Although major milestones have been achieved, the knowledge and potential application in the market of a more efficient hydrogen-based source of energy is still rather limited.

For that reason, the European Council of Innovation (EIC) has launched the 2023 Pathfinder Challenge program to *support research teams to develop high-risk/high-gain science-towards-technology breakthrough research*¹ and find commercially viable solutions for the energy sector, including hydrogen.

One of the projects winning the 2023 edition of Pathfinder Challenge is PhotoSynH2. PhotoSynH2 aims at developing a disruptive technology based on synthetic biology, called photosynthetic electron focussing, for the efficient production of hydrogen using low-cost photosynthetic bacteria (cyanobacteria) genetically re-engineered to exclusively direct the solar energy to hydrogen. To this end, a new type of photobioreactor will be designed, constructed and tested at large-scale in one of the European Member State. This task corresponds to the Work Package n. 6, titled Photobioreactor (PBR) engineering and operation. Under the framework of this work package, a number of activities will be carried out. First, a small-scale Photobioreactor will be constructed as direct evolution of *Synechocystis* and *E. coli* (WP6.1), and it will be tested for optimizing the initial design (WP 6.2). Then, an improved design of the PBR will be carried out and, as a result, a multiplate photobioreactor (MPL) with a capacity of 1300 litre will be constructed (WP. 6.3) and tested for hydrodynamic fluid characterization (WP. 6.4). The final step in the construction journey is to test whether the new photobioreactor (MPL) is fit for industrial application, thus the last task of this work package focuses on identifying prospecting existing locations in Europe where an industrial demo photobioreactor with a capacity of 5,000 liters, could be set up (WP 6.5).

III. About this report

This report takes the reader through the steps taken by the consortium partner Algreen BV in identifying and select suitable locations for testing the industrial demo photobioreactor. The research has been conducted between October 2022 and September 2023. This report is structured as follows: chapter II shortly describes the Pathfinder 2023 Program, the PhotoSynH2 project and the work package 6.4. Chapter IV provides information on the methodology used to carry out the desk research and the stakeholder interviews. Chapter V presents an overview of the European Union journey in regulating GMO and GMM and key elements of the relevant Directives. Chapter VI presents a summary of the findings from the stakeholder interviews and a final recommendation of our team to the consortium on the step forwards.

IV. Research methodology:

To identify the best locations for an industrial photobioreactor testing, the following three criteria were identified:

- GMO regulation compliant: a location is picked if it is suitable to grow, propagate and contain Genetically Modified Organisms
- Flammable gas compliant and a hazardous material: a location is picked if it is capable to handle flammable gases such as Hydrogen.
- Previous experience in handling GMO microalgae or cyanobacteria

If a location fulfilling all criteria cannot be identified in an EU Member State, Algreen B.V. will proceed to survey the most promising locations and frame a pathway for certification (Deliverable 6.5).

As starting point, we carried out a desk-research to scan on the internet using some key words on common online research engines such as Google.com and Bing.com. Among the key words used for the research, there were: GMO, OGM, GMM, Algae, GMO compliant laboratory, fuel, energy sector, hydrogen.

Since the project aims at industrial utilization of GMO, it is important to make an overview of the legal and policy framework currently in force in the EU and the application in member States. Thus, an in-depth study of the current EU policy and regulation on GMO/GMM was part of the research.

Third, we made use of Algreen BV's network in the algae sector to identify a first group of stakeholders to interview on the above topics. Furthermore, we proceeded in using a snowball methodology to expand the network of experts and refine the research: each first round resource person indicated three other key stakeholders available to be contacted and who fall in the following profiles:

- Researchers and Lab Managers at university and/or specialized institute with competence on GMOs, GMMs and/or hydrogen
- Companies operating in microalgae or hydrogen-interested industries
- Business developers (public and private)

Algreen conducted more than 20 interviews with stakeholders from 6 different countries, namely Italy, Netherlands, Portugal, Sweden, Spain and Belgium.

V. European legislation framework:

The entire corpus of GMO legislation was amended, leading to the creation of a new legal framework. Its main legal instruments are:

- Directive 90/219/EEC and follow up Directive 98/81/EC on the contained use of genetically modified microorganisms (GMMs)
- Directive 2001/18/EC on deliberate release into the environment

Directive 90/219/EEC, as amended by Directive 98/81/EC, on the contained use of genetically modified microorganisms (GMMs). This Directive regulates research and industrial work activities involving GMMs (such as genetically modified viruses or bacteria) under conditions of containment, i.e. in a closed environment in which contact with the population and the environment is avoided. This includes work activities in laboratories.

Key elements of Directive 90/219/EEC follow in the paragraph below.

Stated in its objective, the Directive 90/219/EEC aims at laying down common measures for the contained use of genetically modified microorganisms (GMMs) with the ultimate goal of protecting human health and the environment. Such an objective funded its legal root in the

'Environmental Protection article' of the Treaty of Rome. As the scope of the Directive is contained use of GMMs, three procedures are identified based on levels of potential risks for human and the environment. For a case in which a low risk is assessed, the Directive prescribes a simple notification in advance to the authority of the member State indicating both the type of activities and development process of GMMs. In this case, researchers are required to keep record of the activities and/or development of GMOs and ensuring that those are always available for enforcement purpose. Associated with a medium risk for human and the environment, a second and more strict type of procedures is identified. the Directive dictates that a written legal notice (notification) is sent to the competent authorities to declare the contained use of GMOs. In response of the notification, the authorities must check the notification without issuing a specific certificate. At the highest level of risks, the Directive 90/219/EEC prescribes that researchers apply for a licence, that is a written permission issued by the authorities to carry out contained use activities and development of GMOs. In this case, research activities can only start upon receiving the licence. In order to identify the level of risk, the Directive set out the procedures to conduct a risks assessment of the activities related to the contained use. Finally, the directive also defines four classes of contained use and corresponding level of biosafety and other protective measures.

An important moment in the pathway to regulating the use of GMOs, was when the Directive 90/219/EEC was amended by the Directive 98/81/EC, in 1998. In it, the terms '*contained use*' and GMM were better defined and a new and simplified system of classification was introduced with the goal to create a more harmonic set of procedures and protocols.

Another milestone was set when, in 2009, a recast of the Directive 98/81/EC was adopted by the EU. With the official name of 2009/41, the Directive incorporated several amendments as well as it introduced a refined version of the comitology procedures.

Implementation in national regulations of 2009/41

It is important to note that each member state has decided how to implement 2009/41 in its national regulations. For instance, Germany has included 2009/41 in a law on gene technology, while other countries like France, Belgium, Denmark and Sweden included it in the environmental protection regulatory framework. Furthermore, countries like the Netherlands have tighten the control on contained use and request additional details also for containment level 1 and 2. Finally, in Belgium, Denmark and Sweden the scope of national legislation was extended to include both GMM and wild-type pathogens regulated by 2000/54.

An overview of the most important elements of Directive 2001/18/EC are detailed in the following paragraph.

One important building block of the EU regulation on development and use of GMO/GMM is the Directive 2001/18/EC that regulates the deliberate release into the environment. Release should be understood as *the introduction of the GMO into the environment without putting in place confinement measures that prevent contact with the human population or the environment in general*². Two types of activities fall under the Directive 2001/18:

- the experimental release of GMOs into the environment, i.e. the introduction of GMOs into the environment for experimental purposes such as field trials. This matter is regulated by Part B of the Directive;
- the placing on the market of GMOs, for example in case of cultivation, importation or transformation of GMOs into industrial products. This matter is mainly regulated by Part C of the legislation;

The Directive makes a clear distinction between the rules and requirements for release for experimental purpose and the release for commercial purpose. Notwithstanding, in both cases, before the release into the environment the Directive dictates that a risk assessment is conducted.

² Exact definition can be found in the Directive 2001/18/EC

It is worth mention that for GMO food and feed or food and feed products containing or consisting of GMOs the placing on the market was reformed in 2023 and it is now within the scope of Regulation (EC) No 1829/2003. Lastly, Directive 2015/412 amending Directive 2001/18/EC as regards the possibility for the Member States to restrict or prohibit the cultivation of GMOs in their territory.

Besides the two Directives mentioned above, the greatest part of the EU efforts in recent years was directed towards regulating food and feed sectors. Since PhotoSynH2 aims at enhancing the production of hydrogen as innovative and *green* source of energy, other Directives and Regulations are not part of this report.

VI. Stakeholder interview findings and recommendations:

1. About the method

Algreen BV conducted more than 20 interviews with resource persons and experts in the field of algae cultivation, GMOs and GMMs research and development, commercial use of alternative energy source and hydrogen production.

Out of the 20 experts contacted, we interviewed representatives from 5 universities, 5 Research Centre, 6 companies and 4 regulatory or public bodies (Fig. 1).

Figure 1 - Experts' profile

The experts were from a variety of countries: 7 from Italy, 2 from Portugal, 8 from Netherlands, 1 from Sweeden, 1 from Spain, 1 from Belgium (Fig. 2).

Figure 2 - Experts country of origin

The chosen method was based on semi-structured questionnaire. A list of topics was prepared in advanced, however, these topics were discussed with different degree of details depending of the stakeholder's background and time availability. Each meeting lasted between 30 minutes and one hour and it was conducted both online and, when possible, face-to-face.

Given the different area of expertise of the stakeholders, ranging from GMO regulation to marine industry, different approaches were used to deepen into the matter.

2. Findings:

Findings from the stakeholder interviews are grouped in three main topics and discussed in more details below.

Applicable framework:

It becomes clear after talking with several expert that the EU framework for GMO and GMM is geared towards the production of food and feed. Only secondly, pharmaceutical products and sector, like pure enzyme, were addressed during the interviews.

No resource person could point us to an European regulation dealing specifically with the production of energy. In fact, the only regulation that includes fuels and which was mentioned during the interviews is from the United States (Regulation US 3272) on the production of bioethanol from GMO maize.

Despite the lack of specific energy-related GMM regulation, once explained to the experts the aim of the project and the low biosafety level of the process (level 1 out of 4), the majority directed us towards the regulation 2009/41 on '*contained use*'. As noted earlier, even though the Directive has been implemented in different ways into existing national legislation, all countries are obliged to structure the notification procedures around 2 types of permits, one for the facility and one specific for the process intended (i.e. the contained use activities). The Directive does not provide additional specific provisions to member states on how to structure the procedures, roles and competent authorities in charge of the risk assessment and leave ample room of manoeuvre to individual member states. In some countries, contained use activities and/or assessment of the level of containment of the facility has to be simply notified, in other countries these need to be formally assessed and/or authorized separately or in combination.

Procedures:

While discussing the procedures in handling GMMs, experts pointed out that a detection method should be in place before the chosen demonstration facility is ready to operates. It is paramount to be able to detect any DNA spillage into the environment. In addition, experts warned us about the importance of correctly tracking the disposal of the GMM.

Experts part of the European Network of GMOs Laboratories (ENGL) were our primary source of information and many showed interest in collaborating with PhotoSynH2 for writing down laboratory best practices to formulate adequate Standard Operational Procedures (SOP) and support the PBR demonstration implementation activities.

Besides the GMM regulations and requirements, the experts interviewed expressed concern about two additional issues.

First, the stakeholders pointed out that the targeted volume of 5000 liters for the demonstration PBR exceeds the average size of instruments and facilities available at the laboratory scale which currently hold a GMM certification. Thus, it is very unlikely to find a GMM certified laboratory that can work with those volumes.

Second, hydrogen is a gas that needs to be treated carefully and it requires that, for the entire area dedicated to the PBR demonstration, appropriate measurements are in place to handle risk associated with biological production.

Thus, it is of pivotal importance that PhotoSynH2 engages in all necessary steps to ensure that, when the demo PBR for industrial demonstration is ready to operate, it will be able to preserve safety for operator and the environment and comply with EU GMO/GMM regulation.

Lastly, as noted earlier, an important part of PhotoSynH2 work is to design appropriate standard operations measurements. In addition to this, experts highlighted that it is paramount to have a deeper understanding of the type of operations required for ensuring safety for operators and the environment in handling hydrogen gas. Therefore, in selecting a suitable location for an industrial-scale demonstration of hydrogen production, it is recommended to conduct a hazard and operability study (Hazop) and a hazard analysis (Haza).

Hydrogen Production

Many experts raised a point of attention for the project in what concerns the volume needed for the new technology to become attractive in the market. One expert reported that the marine industry has a need to deal with large amount of fuel if one wants to use hydrogen as energy source for transportation in high sea. A more realistic utilization of hydrogen in the industry is using hydrogen-based fuel in leisure transports such as in zero emissions navigation zone (ex. In Norway and Fiord or in canal city like Amsterdam) or as in the case of navigation with yacht.

However, the possibility of using this technology inside the harbors with the possible use of seawater for the production of hydrogen was praised by different experts as a potential opportunity. Experts indicated that multiple European ports are putting forward considerable efforts to become Green Hydrogen HUBs and that this could be a good match with PhotoSynH2 project.

3. Conclusion and recommendations

Considering that the project and technology is totally new and breakthrough, at for now at current status, the outcome of the report is that no location has been identified as of now, but we will extend furthermore and more extensively the research in EU and also outside EU. The recommendation for the consortium is that a place that will be chosen for a potential demo plant of 5.000 MPL, must be appropriate for the handling of GMM in contained use and the safety in handling hydrogen gas following the legislation described as above. During deliverable 6.5 we will discuss of other potential locations.

VII. References:

1. Council Directive 90/219/EEC of 23 April 1990 on the contained use of genetically modified micro-organisms:
[EUR-Lex - 31990L0219 - EN - EUR-Lex \(europa.eu\)](#)
2. Directive 2001/18/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 March 2001 on the deliberate release into the environment of genetically modified organisms and repealing Council Directive 90/220/EEC; *OJ L 106, 17.4.2001, p. 1–39*:
https://eur-lex.europa.eu/resource.html?uri=cellar:303dd4fa-07a8-4d20-86a8-0baaf0518d22.0004.02/DOC_1&format=PDF
3. Directive 2009/41/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 6 May 2009 on the contained use of genetically modified micro-organisms (Recast); *OJ L 125, 21.5.2009, p. 75–97*:
[Directive 2009/41/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 6 May 2009 on the contained use of genetically modified micro-organisms \(Recast\)Text with EEA relevance \(europa.eu\)](#)
4. Belgian legal framework on contained use of GMOs and pathogens:
[Contained Use of GMOs and Pathogens | Belgian Biosafety Server](#)
5. Details on the notification procedures for contained use in the 3 Belgian regions:
<https://www.biosafety.be/content/contained-use-gmos-andor-pathogenic-organisms-notification-procedures>
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[Notification procedures: Clinical Trials with GMOs for human or veterinary use | Belgian Biosafety Server](#)
7. Contained Use of GMOs Ordinance SFS (2000:271) in Sweden
https://www.riksdagen.se/sv/dokument-lagar/dokument/svensk-forfattningssamling/forordning-2000271-om-innesluten-anvandning-av_sfs-2000-271_404 | [Sveriges riksdag \(riksdagen.se\)](#)
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9. Overview of national regulations on genetic engineering in Germany
https://www.bvl.bund.de/EN/06_Genetic_Engineering/03_Applicants/08_LegalFramework/01_Germany/legal_basis_national_node.html
10. Decree No. 2011-1177 on the contained use of GMOs in France:
[Décret n° 2011-1177 du 23 septembre 2011 relatif à l'utilisation confinée d'organismes génétiquement modifiés - Légifrance \(legifrance.gouv.fr\)](#)
11. Executive order on genetic engineering and the working environment in Denmark:
[Siden blev ikke fundet - Arbejdstilsynet \(at.dk\)](#)
12. Decree N. 224 – 8 July 2023 on the contained used of GMOs in Italy:
[DECRETO LEGISLATIVO 8 luglio 2003, n. 224 - Normativa](#)

VIII. Annex I: ENGL members list

Please consult the following webpage:

[ENGL | European Union Reference Laboratory for Genetically Modified Food and Feed \(EURL GMFF\) \(europa.eu\)](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32003R1831&from_uri=https%3A%2F%2Fec.europa.eu/food/rapid-response/rapid-response-2013-01-24-01_en)